

Studies in Conjugated Imines : Addition of Active Methylene Compounds

Nazar Singh and J. S. Sandhu

Michael additions of the active methylene compounds to open-chain system $C = C - C = N$ have not been reported. We report the addition of some active methylene compounds to *N*-cinnamylidenaniline.

The reagents have been found to add to the carbon-nitrogen double bond rather than to yield the expected 1,4-additions. The 1,2-adduct (I) has been found to be stable only in the case of malonic ester. With cyanoacetamide, ethylcyanoacetate, cyanoacetic acid, malonic acid and acetylacetone, the 1,2-adducts initially formed yielded conjugated unsaturated products (II) with elimination of aromatic amines in 70–90% yields. The structures (I) and (II) are assigned by elemental analysis, i.r. spectra and n.m.r. (60 MC/Sec, $CDCl_3$). Their i.r. spectra had bands in the region 950–1000 cm^{-1} (trans $CH = CH$). N.M.R. spectra showed signals for the two olefinic protons below 4τ with a coupling constant of about 16 cps. The configuration of the original trans $CH = CH$ has thus remained unaffected. Structure (II), has been confirmed by the mixed melting points with the corresponding members prepared by condensing cinnamaldehyde with the respective methylene compounds in the presence of piperidine as catalyst in almost quantitative yields. No depression was noted in either case and the melting points were found to be identical with those reported in literature¹⁻⁵.

Structure (III) for the adduct with malononitrile has been assigned by elemental analysis, i.r. spectrum, n.m.r. (60 MC/Sec, $(CD_3)_2SO$) and mass spectrum. Its i.r. spectrum had no bands in the region 800–1000 cm^{-1} (trans $CH = CH$ missing). N.M.R. spectrum was of poor quality but indicated only five aromatic protons as a single large peak rather than the more complex response encountered in the other samples having $-N.C_6H_5$ group, two more acidic protons (one merging with aromatic protons); two olefinic protons as two doublets between 4.5–5.5 τ , but no signal in the range 3–4 τ . The mass spectrum did not have an *M* ion but the fragmentation pattern was found to be consistent with a parent of

1. Fiquet, *Ann. Chem.*, 1893, 29, 493.
- 2 and 3. Day, *Kimmins. Soc.*, 123, 3138.
4. Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 85, 1458.
5. Dutt, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 301.

m/e 246 and corresponded to $C_{15}H_{10}N_4$ as deduced from fragmentation pattern (see below) :

Ion	Intensity	Neutral Fragment lost or equivalent	Empirical Formula (from isotopic distribution)
246	Not present		
219	Weak	HCN	
180	Very intense	$CH_2(CN)_2$	$C_{12}H_8N_2$
165	Weak		
153	Very intense	$CH_2(CN)_2$ HCN	
115	Very intense	$CH_2(CN)_2$ $CH_2(CN)_2$	
104	Very intense		C_8H_8

This fragmentation pattern is consistent with structure III

which may be formed by the 1,2-addition of malonitrile with conjugated imine, followed by elimination of the amine and the subsequent 1,4-addition of the second molecule of malonitrile. Structure (III) was confirmed by the mixed melting point with the product prepared by the addition of malonitrile to cinnamal-malonitrile (m.p. 128°)⁶ prepared by the method indicated above. There was no depression in the mixed melting point.

In addition to the main component (III) the mass spectrum also indicated a minor component giving a M at m/e 248, presumably the saturated analogue of the main component.

The compounds with their characteristics are recorded in Table I.

Our thanks are due to Professor G. W. Kirby, University of Technology, Loughborough, Leicestershire, U.K. for n.m.r. spectra and Dr. E. F. Magoon, Shell Development Company, Emeryville, California, U.S.A. for the mass spectrum.

6. Liebermann, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 1438.

